

Supporting figures_Prajakta Patil et al

Figure 1: a) and b): Viable and non-viable mixture of procured *Ascaris suum* eggs

Figure 2: Electrochemical cell set up at lab scale

Figure 3: a) Cumulative biogas production, variations in the parameters b) pH, c) TS, d) VS, e) VFA, f) CH₄, CO₂, g) H₂S, h) *A. suum* inactivation eggs/ml.

Figure 4: *A. suum* viable eggs (a), (b) and non-viable eggs (c), (d), (e), (f) on 45th day of incubation

Figure 5: *A. suum* viable eggs (a), (b), (c) and non-viable eggs (d), (e), (f) from EC experiment. (g), (e), (f) shows the dissolution of the outer part of the eggshell and subsequent membrane rupture, resulting in complete inactivation of egg in hypochlorite solution.